

Japanese Figures in the Video Game Industry: Hironobu Sakaguchi (I)

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To speak about the video game industry without mentioning some of its great minds is impossible. Among them stands Hironobu Sakaguchi, a figure behind truly legendary titles which, over the years, contributed to the growth of video games into what we now recognise as a powerful industry, comparable to cinema or even tourism.

The beginnings of Sakaguchi: from musician to video game creator

The work of creatives such as Hironobu Sakaguchi proved to be one of the most evident pillars in this transformation of video games into something far beyond mere entertainment. In particular, his involvement in the series that brought him worldwide recognition: Final Fantasy. However, as will be seen throughout this article, his contribution to this franchise was by no means his only noteworthy achievement. Even so, it remains essential when analysing the trajectory of this professional.

Sakaguchi was born in 1962 in Hitachi, in the prefecture of Ibaraki. From a young age, he planned to become part of the world of music, even participating in several groups and bands, while also organising concerts, at times selling tickets himself. Nevertheless, his studies were not directly related to this field. Realising that the success he sought was not arriving as quickly as he had hoped, he began studying electronic engineering at the Yokohama National University, after developing a strong interest in computers. He left his studies in 1983 alongside another future member of Square, Hiromichi Tanaka.

During his studies, the young Sakaguchi significantly deepened his interest in programming and computer engineering in general. In particular, he aspired to own a well-known computer of the time: the successful Apple II, one of the earliest personal computers and a key factor in propelling Apple to the position it holds today.

He was unable to acquire this machine due to its cost, but instead obtained a generic version that served his needs, although it also proved costly. To make matters worse, Sakaguchi could not afford the various software programmes he required for his computer, which led him to seek part-time employment... and it was at this point that he encountered his destiny.

Hironobu Sakaguchi's entry into Square

While searching for work, Sakaguchi came across a job opportunity at a newly created division part of an electric company, dedicated to video game development. A division known as Square. Its founder, Masafumi Miyamoto, aimed not to rely on programmers from diverse specialisations, but rather to build a team of professionals trained and focused exclusively on video game development.

This is how Sakaguchi entered the world of video games. Once again, as with other major figures in the industry, a combination of luck, chance, and the vision of an entrepreneur interested in a new business model—much like in the case of Shigeru Miyamoto and Hiroshi Yamauchi—led to the emergence of a new video game company.

Masafumi Miyamoto—centre, wearing glasses—alongside Hironobu Sakaguchi—immediately to Miyamoto's right in the image—and Hiromichi Tanaka—both making a victory gesture, although Tanaka partially covers his face with his left hand—together with the rest of the team that would later become Square Co., Ltd.

Sakaguchi's interest in video games continued to grow, and his dedication and talent led him to quickly rise to the position of Director of Planning and Development at Square. However, he did not achieve commercial success with any of his projects for the company until, inspired by the success of titles such as *Dragon Quest*—developed by what would become Square's long-time rival, Enix—he decided to push forward with the creation of a new RPG (Role-Playing Game). This was an idea he had been eager to realise for years.

The project was initially to be called *Fighting Fantasy*, but Sakaguchi renamed it *Final Fantasy*, as he considered it his “final fantasy”—a last attempt to achieve success for his company.

At that time, RPGs were far from the established and widely beloved genre they would later become. Nevertheless, the team committed fully to their new project, and Square eventually placed its trust in Sakaguchi and supported him. It was not an easy process, particularly because Square had initially refused to allow him to develop an RPG until its executives witnessed the overwhelming success of *Dragon Quest*.

Sakaguchi drew inspiration not only from this Japanese title but also from Western role-playing games that had become highly popular in Japan, such as the Wizardry series—first released in 1981—and *Ultima*, also launched in 1981. Following a series of setbacks, Sakaguchi once again questioned whether he had chosen the right path by pursuing a career in the video game industry. He even considered that *Final Fantasy* would be his final project before returning to his university studies, which he had abandoned to enter the world of video games.

The primary system for which the team was developing the game was the successful Family Computer (Famicom)—known in the West as the Nintendo Entertainment System (NES). The team assembled for *Final Fantasy* was larger than usual, and the company ultimately entrusted Sakaguchi with the role of director.

Sakaguchi did not give up and chose to defend *Final Fantasy* wholeheartedly, much like the Warrior of Light—the title later given to the canonical protagonist of the first game. His determination and commitment to creating something new within the industry—something that would stand out and save not only his career and that of his colleagues, but also the company itself, which was facing financial difficulties—ultimately led to the success of *Final Fantasy*.

The rest, as they say, is history.

Sakaguchi brought together other industry professionals to work on *Final Fantasy*, such as Kōichi Ishii—creator of the later Seiken Densetsu series (known in the West as *Mana*)—and Akitoshi Kawazu, responsible for the SaGa series, as well as titles such as *The Last Remnant*, and who also contributed to later entries in *Final Fantasy* and the aforementioned *Mana* series.

Among these figures was also Nobuo Uematsu, the composer of the soundtrack for the first *Final Fantasy*, who would go on to become a close friend and frequent collaborator of Sakaguchi. His work holds a central place in many of Sakaguchi's titles.

With influences ranging from classical and Celtic music to rock, Uematsu is widely regarded as one of the finest composers in the video game industry. His music—beginning with the main theme of *Final Fantasy*—is instantly recognisable and deeply associated with the franchise.

Through the following link, you can listen to an orchestral version of this theme, performed by the London Philharmonic Orchestra.

Final Fantasy was designed to take full advantage of the technical capabilities and architecture of the NES, while also drawing heavily on board games and tabletop role-playing systems. It introduced mechanics such as elemental strengths and weaknesses in combat—features not yet common in Japanese RPGs at the time. Players could choose between different character classes and assemble a party of four protagonists, even selecting their names, thereby enabling a level of customisation similar to that found in traditional tabletop role-playing games.

The protagonists embark on a journey across multiple continents, exploring dungeons filled with monsters, all in order to fulfil their destiny as saviours of the world, marked by the four crystals they carry.

The protagonists of *Final Fantasy* in a magic shop—another of the many elements drawn from tabletop and board role-playing games present in the title

Final Fantasy was a resounding success and ultimately saved Square from bankruptcy, allowing the company to become one of the leading forces in the industry. Indeed, Square went on to specialise almost exclusively in RPGs, aside from titles such as *Tobal No. 1* and later entries in that fighting game series, in which Hironobu Sakaguchi was also involved.

As we now know, the then young Sakaguchi did not have to leave the industry, nor did Square collapse. Instead, both continued to grow and evolve throughout the 1980s and 1990s. Ironically, Square initially planned to release only 200,000 copies of *Final Fantasy*, but Sakaguchi pushed for double that number. This decision proved crucial, as sales volume was directly tied to the number of ROM cartridges manufactured.

The risk was enormous: if the game failed, the financial losses would be severe; yet if demand exceeded supply, that too could have been disastrous. Once again, this was a bold gamble by Sakaguchi in defence of his project.

Sakaguchi and the consolidation of the RPG within the video game industry

Although RPGs had gradually entered Japan during the late 1970s and throughout the 1980s, it was not until titles such as *Dragon Quest* by Enix and *Final Fantasy* by Square—alongside other important works such as the Ys series by Nihon Falcom, which began in 1987—that the Japanese role-playing game industry became firmly established. The success of home consoles made the genre more accessible and popular, as many households owned gaming systems as a form of entertainment, particularly due to the widespread success of platforms such as the Family Computer.

Hironobu Sakaguchi was one of the key figures responsible for shaping the JRPG (Japanese Role-Playing Game) as we understand it today. These are role-playing games characterised by clear influences from anime, manga, and broader Asian—particularly Japanese—cultural aesthetics, including visual style and recurring character archetypes.

The video game industry experienced a period of growth which, in Japan and later abroad, paralleled that of anime and manga. These three industries expanded progressively, coinciding with Japan's increasing openness to the West and the export of major cultural works to international audiences. The first *Final Fantasy* was not released worldwide, but only in Japan and the United States—where it achieved a level of success that Sakaguchi himself had not anticipated—aligning with Nintendo's efforts to establish a presence in the American market through Nintendo of America. Subsequent titles such as *Final Fantasy II* and *III*, which introduced new mechanics, did not reach international audiences until years later.

It was not until the early 1990s that Square reintroduced *Final Fantasy* to Western markets with its fourth instalment—one of the most beloved entries in the series. In 1991, *Final Fantasy IV* was released, taking full advantage of the graphical and audio capabilities of the Super Famicom—known outside Japan as the Super Nintendo Entertainment System (Super NES or SNES).

Final Fantasy IV was released in the West under the title *Final Fantasy II* and stood out for its memorable characters and layered storytelling. The narrative follows the fall and redemption of the knight Cecil, alongside Rosa, his beloved, and his closest companions, forming a group defined more by friendship than mere alliance.

The game featured significant plot twists, as well as a compelling antagonist in Golbez—who ultimately proves more complex than initially perceived. Its narrative depth and dramatic tone marked a clear departure from earlier, simpler stories designed merely to accompany gameplay. Instead, storytelling became a defining element of the experience—a focus on dramatic narrative that the franchise has continued to uphold ever since.

Character design was led by Yoshitaka Amano, who had already contributed to the Final Fantasy series since its inception. Already a renowned artist in Japan at the time, Amano played a crucial role in shaping the franchise's visual identity. His distinctive style—colourful, intricate, expressive, and often featuring androgynous characters—drew heavily on traditional Japanese art and became one of the defining features of the series as it rose to international prominence during the 1990s.

Character design of the summoner Rydia from *Final Fantasy IV*, by Yoshitaka Amano

Following *Final Fantasy IV*, a title that achieved market success—leading to Hironobu Sakaguchi being promoted to vice president at Square—came *Final Fantasy V* in 1992.

This was the last title directed by Sakaguchi himself, who chose to hand over direction to Yoshinori Kitase for *Final Fantasy VI*, released in 1994 (known in the West as *Final Fantasy III*, as *Final Fantasy V* was never originally released outside Japan on the SNES and appeared internationally only years later on other platforms). Kitase had previously worked as a scenario writer for *Final Fantasy V* and had a long-standing relationship of trust with Sakaguchi, who recognised his ability to craft dramatic scenes and to situate them within a compelling narrative context.

Final Fantasy VI also introduced a young artist, Tetsuya Nomura, who would become a regular contributor to Square's titles and develop a highly recognisable personal style closely associated with the Final Fantasy franchise.

Many enthusiasts regard *Final Fantasy VI* as the pinnacle of the series, and it is reportedly Sakaguchi's personal favourite—he later changed his mind after releasing *Final Fantasy IX*, which became his favourite final Final Fantasy until today. The game offered memorable characters, a charismatic villain in Kefka, diverse locations, and influences ranging from medieval to steampunk and science-fiction aesthetics. Its story was immersive and full of surprises, accompanied by a soundtrack composed once again by Nobuo Uematsu, which elevated the emotional impact of the game to unprecedented levels.

As an example, one can listen to a segment from the opera *Maria and Draco*, specifically the *Aria di mezzo carattere*, in which Celes Chere—one of the game's protagonists—performs as Maria, a woman caught in a tragic love story. The SNES sound chip was utilised to its fullest, even emulating character voices synchronised with the music across multiple audio channels. The result remains one of the most memorable cutscenes in video game history.

The 1990s are often referred to as the “Golden Age of RPGs”. Square's portfolio included renowned franchises such as *Seiken Densetsu* —*Mana in the West*—, but the era also saw the release of *Super Mario RPG: Legend of the Seven Stars* (1996), which even involved Shigeru Miyamoto, creator of the Mario franchise, and *Chrono Trigger* (1995). Sakaguchi contributed to *Chrono Trigger* as a game designer, collaborating with Akira Toriyama—celebrated for works such as *Dr. Slump* and *Dragon Ball*—who provided concept art. The project also included Yūji Horii, creator of *Dragon Quest*, illustrating the collaboration of personnel across competing companies, Square and Enix. *Chrono Trigger* is widely regarded as one of the greatest RPGs in history.

A very young Yasunori Mitsuda contributed to the soundtrack; however, due to illness caused by the intense workload and long hours he devoted to his first major composition project, he had to withdraw before completing the score, which was finished by Nobuo Uematsu. Mitsuda later went on to compose for major RPG titles, including the *Xeno* series, beginning with *Xenogears* (1998) for Sony's first PlayStation.

Alongside other significant franchises from this era and earlier—such as Phantasy Star (created by Rieko Kodama in 1987, for Sega), SaGa (including the Romancing Saga subseries), Square’s own Final Fantasy series, Namco’s Tales series, and Quintet’s Soul Blazer trilogy (1992), *Illusion of Time* (1995), and *Terranigma* (1996)—the work of Hironobu Sakaguchi and his team helped consolidate the Japanese role-playing game genre. Their influence continues to shape the industry to this day, alongside Sakaguchi’s ongoing contributions.

Sources

- **Texts consulted:** Domenech Alcaide, Andrés, (2017), *Los videojuegos como producto del arte: La influencia e importancia del dibujo, del cómic y otras artes en su historia* (Doctoral thesis), University of Granada, Granada; A 90s Kid; Forbes | **Text created by:** Andrés Domenech Alcaide [CoolJapan.es]
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